

DETERMINISTIC DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING OF CARBON NANOTUBE STAPLE YARNS

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Keywords: *carbon nanotube, yarns, fiber, strength, joint*

1. Introduction

High performance fibers are increasingly sought as building blocks of light-weight, durable, and energy efficient structural materials, for applications including sports gear, boat hulls, wind turbines, and airplanes [1]. Inspired by natural materials, where the hierarchical structure and organization of fibers determine their collective chemical and physical functionalities, [2, 3] future multifunctional fibers will combine high mechanical performance (stiffness, strength, damping, durability), with self-sensing, actuation, and/or energy storage capability. This can be enabled by scalable synthesis of nanoscale building blocks such as carbon nanotubes (CNT), and engineer load transfer among those building blocks to scale up their properties, isolate defects, dissipate vibration, and/or to amplify stiffness.[4, 5]

Individual CNTs are well established to have outstanding mechanical strength (~ 50 GPa), high electrical and thermal conductivity ($\sim \mu\Omega\text{-cm}$ for multi-walled (MW)-NT, $3000 \text{ Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) at low mass density ($< 2200 \text{ kg/m}^3$). As a result, CNT fibers have been considered a possible replacement for high strength carbon-based fibers for load bearing applications, and in the nearer term are attractive for lightweight electrical wires. Therefore, a high commercial value is driving the development of manufacturing technologies that can efficiently transform high-quality CNTs into continuous high-performance fibers. Inspired by the actuation mechanism of natural fibrous materials, artificial muscles were recently fabricated from CNT yarns impregnated with paraffin wax.[6]

There are three mainstream approaches to CNT fiber fabrication: solution-phase, solid-state, and gas-phase spinning. In solution-phase spinning, CNTs are first dispersed in liquid, and subsequently assembled into a fiber such as by extrusion through a spinneret, and optionally combined with a polymer

binder [7-13]. In the solid-state approach, CNTs are drawn from a vertically aligned CNT forest, and twisted into a yarn [14, 15]. Because of entanglement and surface interactions between CNTs within the forest, pulling on a group of CNTs causes the forest to unravel in an accordion-like manner, if the structural characteristics of the CNT forest are suitable for spinning. In the gas-phase approach, CNT growth from a floating catalyst (typically derived from an organometallic precursor) forms a low-density network of CNTs, which is drawn and/or spun into a fiber upon exiting the furnace. [16, 17] The gas phase approach has been studied by Windle and colleagues at the University of Cambridge, and has been concurrently developed and commercialized by Nanocomp Technologies in the United States, and by Q-Flo in Europe. As pursued by Nanocomp, the gas phase method can also create nonwoven CNT sheets by deposition of the floating CNT network onto a belt at the outlet of the furnace. Likewise, the solid-state method can be used to draw CNT from forests into thin aligned sheets having very low density [18].

The yarns produced by Windle and colleagues, made by direct gas phase spinning followed by capillary densification, have an average strength of 1 N/Text, which is equivalent to $1 \text{ GPa}/(\text{g/cm}^3)$. This value is smaller than commercially available Kevlar ($\sim 3 \text{ N/Text}$), Dyneema ($\sim 3.5 \text{ N/Text}$) and high strength carbon fibers.[19] Nonetheless, these yarns still have higher strength than other twisted CNT yarns, usually made from MWNT, mainly because they comprise few-walled CNTs that self-collapse in the furnace creating large contact area for load transfer.[14] However, strength exceeding 6.5 N/Text when the sample length (2 mm) is comparable to the individual CNT length, demonstrating the potential of CNT yarns.

To make stronger CNT yarns, better understanding of the morphology and strength of

nanoscale contacts among CNTs is needed, along with new scalable technologies for continuous yarn manufacturing. Toward this goal, end we present a new method to fabricate continuous staple yarns from long CNTs, by mechanical rolling and twisting of millimeter-long CNT microstructures that are first grown as vertically aligned (VA-)CNT “forests”. This process leads to new insights about the load transfer and failure mechanism of CNT yarns, and could potentially enable CNT yarns with tunable mechanical and multifunctional properties via the design of the internal joints.

2. Yarn manufacturing process

First, VA-CNTs (“forests”) are synthesized by atmospheric pressure chemical vapor deposition (CVD).

Fig. 1 CNT staple yarn manufacturing process. (a) Schematic. (b) SEM images of CNT lines before (top) after (middle) rolling and after delamination (bottom). (c) A 5 mm yarn mounted in the tensile test apparatus.

The CNTs are formed as parallel slender blades of μm -scale width and mm-scale length as shown in

Fig. 1.[20] The geometry and spacing of the CNT blades are defined by photolithography and lift-off of the catalyst pattern, comprising of a sputtered thin film of 1 nm Fe supported by 10 nm Al_2O_3 . The catalyst pattern substrates are heated to and annealed at 775°C in 400:100 sccm H_2 :He (10 minutes ramp, 10 minutes hold), and then CNT growth proceeds in a mixture of (100:400:100) H_2 :He: C_2H_4 . [21] The CNTs within the forest usually have diameter $d \approx 10$ nm, height $h \approx 0.5$ mm (for 12 minutes growth), and density $\rho \approx 30 \mu\text{g}/\text{mm}^3$ (specific gravity $\text{SG} = 0.03 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$) as measured using a high-precision scale.

Next, we mechanically roll the CNT blades to transform them into continuous strips of horizontally-aligned (HA-) CNTs [20], as shown in **Fig. 1**. The CNT segments are densified by contact with half-a-millimeter-diameter metal rolling pin. The horizontally aligned (HA-)CNT films have smaller thickness ($<10\%$ of the original line pattern thickness) and higher packing density. By controlling the rolling induced Hertzian stress, which scales proportionally with the normal force applied to the roller, the CNT assemblies are compacted while retaining their highly aligned geometry without breaking the individual CNTs. After the rolling process, significant further densification is achieved by infiltrating the HA-CNTs with an organic solvent such as acetone, and subsequently evaporating the solvent. As a result, the thinnest and most uniform HA-CNT sheets are achieved by combining mechanical and capillary densification methods. Raman spectroscopy shows that the G/D peak intensity ratio is invariant before and after rolling and densification, therefore suggesting that the CNT quality is not compromised during the rolling and densification steps. [20]

As shown in **Fig. 1** the process can be used to fabricate strips of 1 cm length (limited by substrate size), 200 to 1 mm width and 2 to 20 μm thickness (controlled by line pattern) with unidirectional CNTs by rolling and overlapping newly formed dense CNT segments. Further, high resolution SEM images show that the capillary densification after rolling causes the CNTs to densify and interpenetrate within the overlap region therefore causing the overlapping segments to adhere by increasing the contact area among CNTs at the joint. This “capillary joining” step is essential to create contiguous staple CNT assemblies for tension testing. We refer to these as “staple yarns”, which can be delaminated off the

substrates and then directly tested, or optionally twisted prior to testing.

3. Yarn properties and failure mechanics

Fig. 2 shows SEM images of a CNT yarn after peeling and testing, indicating the details of the joints. The shown yarn has 500 μm width and 3 μm thickness. The segments were grown to a height of 600 μm from a line pattern with 20 μm thickness and 300 μm spacing, leading to an overlap of 50% after rolling. After rolling, the CNTs were densified by condensation of acetone on the substrate and subsequent evaporation. This step is essential for joining the segments and peeling them off the substrate. The specific gravity of the free standing yarns after peeling is close to 0.3 g/cm^3 . We measured the tensile stiffness and strength of CNT yarns, each approximately 3-4 mm long, using a custom built tensile testing machine with a S-beam load cell (Futek).

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image showing the overlapping segments before twisting. (b) High resolution SEM image showing the junction. (c) SEM image of the twisted CNT yarn (d) Stress-strain curves of CNT yarns tested in tension, where one was twisted after peeling.

Fig. 2 shows stress strain data for 2 yarns having the same geometry and grown under the same

conditions, where one was twisted. For the untwisted yarn the stiffness (slope of stress-strain curve during loading) and strength (failure stress) are 1.3 N/TeX and 0.13 N/TeX respectively. SEM images (Fig. 2b) of the strongest yarns from this study after testing show that the failure typically occurs within the continuous CNT segments and not at the inter-segment interface. Notably, for this yarn, the loading curve exhibits a sharp drop in load at 0.1 strain; however, as the extension continues, the yarn recovers its stiffness, and stretches an additional 5% until breakage at 0.15 strain. The drop in stiffness after the discontinuity is small (only a few %). Length measurements of the overlapping segments show no signs of slip except at the location of the failure where large slip lengths are observed. This may be due to nanoscale stick-slip events occurring as the load on the CNT strips is increased. This mechanism is typical for fibers based on hierarchical assembly of short constituent fibers, and has been studied for example in wood.[2] Stick-slip in wood fibers is characterized by the presence of discontinuities in stress-strain relations, after which the strips can almost restore their initial stiffness.

We find that twisting increases the ultimate strength and strain, and that sudden slip is not apparent in twisted yarns. The yarn twisted by 3 turns/mm (**Fig. 2c-d**) showed a strength enhancement of about 70% to 0.22 N/TeX by mitigating the local fractures both at the CNT segments and joints. The enhancement in stiffness due to twisting is 30% to 1.7 N/TeX (at strain < 0.02); we believe this is due to the induced misalignment (45°) between the yarn's axial direction and the CNT alignment.[22]

We now consider the failure mechanism of our yarns, as related to the intrinsic strength of the CNT segments and the joints. To achieve high strength at low mass density, CNT yarns must comprise just enough CNTs to bare the load without idly contributing to added mass density. The effective strength of CNT yarns is therefore

$$\sigma_{yarn} \left[\frac{\text{GPa}}{\text{SG}} \right] = \text{MIN} \{ \sigma_f, \sigma_c \} / \rho_{yarn}$$

Here, σ_c is the contact strength between overlapping CNTs at the interface, σ_f is the intrinsic strength of the free length at the CNT segments, and ρ_{yarn} is the mass density of the yarns expressed in (SG) g/cm^3 .

This is analogous to the failure of a chain at its weakest link. The yarns can break by failure of individual segments along their length σ_f , and failure at the interface between two segments σ_c . The strength of the segments along their free length is

$$\sigma_f [GPa] = S_{CNT} \cdot \rho_a$$

Here, S_{CNT} is the individual CNT effective strength which depends on the quality (wall perfection, crystallinity) resulting from the synthesis conditions, ρ_a is the number of CNTs per unit area in the (here) densified CNT segment. Notably the yarn geometry can be tuned by the pattern design and the growth height. It is known that a continuous CNT assembly comprising <100 CNTs fail due to weak load transfer across the cross section as confirmed by in situ MEMS testing showing sword-sheath failure mode where the CNT within the bundles separate from the CNTs at the circumference due to tension [23, 24]. The contact strength can be written as

$$\sigma_c [GPa] = \tau_c \cdot A_c / A_{cs}$$

where τ_c is the shear strength of the interface, A_c is the interface area and A_{cs} is the total cross section area of the yarn which depends on the segment thickness and the number of segments. The density of the yarn is

$$\rho_{yarn} [g/cm^3] = W_{unit\ length} \cdot \rho_a$$

$W_{unit\ length}$ is the weight of individual CNTs per unit length.

The ratio of the VA-CNT height to the spacing between the CNT blades determines the overlapping length among the CNT segments and the number of layers in the yarn, and hence its thickness as shown in **Fig. 3**. By fabricating and testing yarns with different pattern dimensions, we therefore studied the effect of the overlapping length and the number of segment layers as shown in **Fig. 3b**. In light of the equations above, we expected that, beyond the unknown overlap distance at which $\sigma_c = \sigma_f$, the addition of layers would not further increase the strength. On the other hand, the additional layers contribute to the mass density so the specific strength would be reduced. Indeed, for lines of 20 μm thickness, we observe that the strength (N/Text) drops as the number of layers is increased, indicating that the contact strength σ_c is not proportionally

scaling with the addition of layers. This is possibly due to the coupling and buckling of the tall CNT blades during rolling because of their aspect ratio and closed spacing.[25]

Fig. 3 (a) Schematic of a CNT yarn with 3.2 layers showing the continuous rolled segments and overlapping joints. (b) Measured relationship between yarn strength and number of layers.

We also note that for maximum yarn strength $S_{CNT}/W_{unit\ length}$ should be increased by synthesizing large diameter few-walled CNTs. These equations also predict that the areal density affects the yarn performance by increasing the effective contact area among the CNTs at the interface and hence contributing to τ_c ; as well as the load transfer among the CNTs within the individual segments. In previous studies, we have shown that VA-CNTs show higher strength both in tension [26] and compression [27] when densified by condensation and evaporation of acetone due to elastocapillary forming and the creation of new nanoscale contacts among the CNTs. Finally, the A_c/A_{cs} in the nominator of the *MIN* function highlights the need to make segments with small thickness (i.e. thin blades) and to improve nanoscale interpenetration of the CNTs from neighboring segments to achieve the highest strength.

Further, the measured stiffness and strength of our CNT yarns are comparable to previous measurements of individual VA-CNT

microstructures prepared in our growth system. The individual microstructures (which have continuous CNTs and no joints) have average strength of 0.25 N/Tex [26]. Therefore, we find that interpenetrated CNT joints formed by rolling and capillary densification of CNT line patterns can withstand large shear stresses at the segments' contact interface and that the limiting mechanism on their maximum strength (for continuous and overlapping CNTs) is similar, and can be related to efficient load transfer among neighboring CNTs within the same forest.

Fig. 4 Modeling the strength of CNT junction. (a) Side view schematic of 2 overlapping CNTs. (b) Cross-section of deformed contact geometry as modeled using energy balance method. (c) Predicted strength vs. % overlap for various CNT geometries.

Last, we built an analytical model to analyze the load transfer in the yarns by considering the intrinsic strength of individual CNTs, and the strength of the contacts among individual overlapping CNTs as shown in Fig 4a. We model the strength of the contact between two overlapping CNTs by calculating the deformation of the cross-section of each individual CNT. The equilibrium contact width between the CNT cross-sections is obtained by minimizing the sum of van der Waals and strain energy due to deformation [28]. We then obtain the contact strength from a microscale multi-asperity friction law between the deformed CNTs and the

interfacial shear strength per unit area between CNTs, reported in the literature [29]. The intrinsic strength of CNTs is calculated assuming that the walls to behave like rolled-up defect-free monolayer graphene, and that all the walls bear load uniformly. **Fig. 4c** shows the effective strength of the yarn for CNTs with different diameters and number of walls. Our calculations predict the percent (ideal) overlap required to have effective yarn strength equivalent to the intrinsic CNT strength. For example, yarns made from double walled CNT of 4 nm diameter could reach 112 N/Tex strength if the CNT have 53% overlap length. **Fig. 4** shows strengths for $L_{total} = 5\mu\text{m}$. The model shows that, depending on variables in CNT yarn design, the strength can be limited either by the contact or by the intrinsic CNT strength. Hence, in principle it is possible to design a CNT yarn with a deterministic strength, and to choose the contact geometry that may more effectively transmit the intrinsic CNT strength; however, the waviness of CNTs within yarns made by known manufacturing methods including that presented here, causes small periodic contacts rather than long parallel contacts.

4. Conclusion

We have shown that CNT staple yarns can be made directly from patterned CNT forests by rolling and capillary joining to tune the yarn strength. Straight yarns (no twisting) have strength ranging from 0.03 to 0.13 N/Tex, and reaching 0.22 N/Tex for twisted yarns. Observed trends of strength with yarn joint geometry, along with a model of CNT-CNT contact strength, give insights on how CNT yarn strength can be tuned based on both intrinsic CNT strength and extrinsic CNT-CNT contact geometry and strength.

5. Acknowledgements

Financial support to S.T. and A.J.H., and funds for fabrication and testing, were provided by the Office of Naval Research (YIP Award N000141210815). A.R. was supported by a University of Michigan Mechanical Engineering Department Fellowship. Microfabrication and catalyst deposition were carried out in the Lurie Nanofabrication Facility (LNF) and microscopy in the Electron Micro Analysis Lab (EMAL).

6. References

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